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Hospitality English Vocabulary Mastery: A Qualitative Descriptive Study on Student Performance with Wordwall Games

Sri Ariyanti Sabiku

Jurusan Pariwisata, Universitas Negeri Gorontalo
Email korespondensi: sriariyantisabiku@ung.ac.id

Abstract

This study aims to evaluate English vocabulary mastery among tourism students in the hospitality sector. Seven key areas of vocabulary proficiency were assessed, encompassing basic hotel vocabulary, travel and tourism terminology, hotel systems and operations, hotel services and amenities, room types, marketing and promotion, and hotel department functions. A qualitative descriptive method was employed, involving 26 purposively sampled tourism students from Universitas Negeri Gorontalo during the even semester of the 2023-2024 academic year. Data were collected through direct observation and vocabulary tests, designed using four game-based activities on the Wordwall platform: wordsearch, anagram, gameshow quiz, and match-up. The findings reveal significant variation in vocabulary mastery across different topics. The "Travel and Tourism Terminology" topic achieved the highest average score at 89%, followed by "Hotel Services and Amenities" at 71%, "Basic Hotel Vocabulary" at 63%, "Hotel Department Functions" at 59%, "Room Types" at 54%, "Marketing and Promotion" at 48%, and "Hotel Systems and Operations" at 37%. The "Wordsearch" and "Gameshow Quiz" games were found to be easier, "Match Up" presented a moderate to high level of difficulty, and "Anagram" was the most challenging, requiring quick and logical thinking. The study highlights the need for increased focus on topics with lower vocabulary proficiency to enhance student competence. It recommends the use of Wordwall as an effective instructional tool, but it should be integrated with supplementary teaching strategies to address the challenges in mastering specific vocabulary.

Keywords: English Vocabulary Mastery, Hospitality Sector, Wordwall Games

Abstrak

Penelitian ini bertujuan untuk mengevaluasi penguasaan kosakata bahasa Inggris di kalangan mahasiswa Jurusan Pariwisata Universitas Negeri Gorontalo. Tujuh topik utama penguasaan kosakata yang dievaluasi mencakup Kosakata Dasar Perhotelan, Terminologi Perjalanan dan Pariwisata, Sistem dan Operasional Hotel, Layanan dan Fasilitas Hotel, Jenis Kamar, Pemasaran dan Promosi, serta Fungsi Departemen Hotel. Metode deskriptif kualitatif digunakan dalam penelitian ini dengan melibatkan 26 mahasiswa Semester Genap Tahun Akademik 2023-2024. Data dikumpulkan melalui observasi langsung dan tes kosakata yang dirancang dengan empat jenis permainan pada platform Wordwall: *wordsearch*, *anagram*, *gameshow quiz*, dan *match up*. Hasil penelitian menunjukkan variasi signifikan dalam penguasaan kosakata antar topik. Topik "Terminologi Perjalanan dan Pariwisata" memperoleh skor tertinggi dengan rata-rata 89%, diikuti oleh "Layanan dan Fasilitas Hotel" sebesar 71%, "Kosakata Dasar Perhotelan" sebesar 63%, "Fungsi Departemen Hotel" sebesar 59%, "Jenis Kamar" sebesar 54%, "Pemasaran dan Promosi" sebesar 48%, dan "Sistem dan Operasional Hotel" sebesar 37%. Sementara itu, permainan "Wordsearch" dan "Gameshow Quiz" dinilai lebih mudah, "Match Up" berada pada tingkat kesulitan menengah hingga tinggi, sedangkan "Anagram" menjadi yang paling menantang karena membutuhkan pemikiran cepat dan logis. Studi ini menekankan perlunya fokus lebih besar pada topik-topik dengan penguasaan kosakata yang lebih rendah untuk meningkatkan kompetensi mahasiswa. Penelitian ini merekomendasikan penggunaan Wordwall sebagai alat pembelajaran yang efektif, namun perlu diintegrasikan dengan strategi pembelajaran tambahan untuk mengatasi tantangan dalam penguasaan kosakata tertentu.

Kata Kunci: Penguasaan Kosakata Bahasa Inggris, Sektor Perhotelan, Permainan Wordwall

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INTRODUCTION

The hospitality sector within the tourism industry, which is heavily service-oriented, demands a workforce with strong communication skills, particularly in English. Proficiency in English is essential for various services, such as booking, providing assistance, and handling complaints, to ensure efficient and high-quality service delivery (Firharmawan et al., 2022). To enhance verbal communication skills, it is crucial to have an adequate command of English vocabulary. This vocabulary mastery serves as the fundamental building block of language skills and plays a critical role. Kuncoro (2017) demonstrated a significant correlation between vocabulary mastery and speaking skills among second-year students at Universitas Indraprasta PGRI, with a significance value of 0.000 ($p < 0.05$) and a t-value of 3.694 (greater than the t-table value of 1.69). This finding is one of several studies that support the argument that vocabulary mastery significantly influences speaking skills and underscores the importance of effective teaching methods.

In line with the growing communication demands within the hospitality sector, various English language learning strategies have been developed. Fithriyani and Anggraeni (2023) analyzed vocabulary mastery among students at SMK Pariwisata Tegal, finding that strategies such as regular reading, asking questions to teachers, group discussions, the use of audio-visual media, and memorization techniques were perceived by students as effective methods for enhancing vocabulary mastery. Anggreni and Antara (2019) highlighted the importance of intensive training through continuous interaction in speaking skills, with the guided conversation method showing significant improvement in students' speaking abilities. Dina et al. (2022) reported the success of game-based and film-based training in enhancing students' English language skills, which positively impacted their motivation and academic performance.

Technological advancements have also introduced new methods of English language learning. Sadikin and Lutfiyah (2023) demonstrated that learning applications enhance material comprehension and confidence in English usage, offering flexibility in the learning process. During the COVID-19 pandemic, strategies like Wordwall became essential, with research by Sirait, Panjaitan, and Saragih (2022) highlighting its effectiveness in remote learning scenarios. Wordwall, as an online-based application, proved to be effective in enhancing student engagement and the vocabulary learning process. Furthermore, research by Aprilia et al. (2023) found that the Wordwall platform is effective as an evaluative tool for improving language skills among students in rural high schools. In addition to creating a comfortable evaluation atmosphere, this research emphasizes the need for teacher proficiency in utilizing Wordwall optimally to foster creativity in the development of evaluation questions.

The Tourism Department at Universitas Negeri Gorontalo aims to produce professional and competent graduates equipped with the knowledge and skills required by the industry, supported by a curriculum design that aligns with the program's mission and goals. The curriculum structure emphasizes the enhancement of English communication skills tailored to various occupational needs within the hospitality sector. Among the courses that support the development of these English communication skills is the Hotel English Conversation course, offered in the second semester. This course aims to introduce students to the essential vocabulary, expressions, and common phrases used in hotel environments while also enhancing their communication abilities in operational hotel scenarios. The course instructor utilizes various online learning media, including the Wordwall application. Therefore, this study aims to evaluate the English vocabulary mastery of students in the hospitality sector using the Wordwall application. The primary research focuses on: 1) What is the level of English vocabulary mastery among students in the hospitality field? 2) Which topics present the greatest challenge for students in mastering English vocabulary in the hospitality sector? 3) How effective are the four types of games within the wordwall application in facilitating vocabulary mastery?

This study can provide new insights into the level of vocabulary mastery, identify topics that require increased focus in the curriculum design of the Hotel English Conversation course, and evaluate the effectiveness of the four game-based media and their contributions to vocabulary learning. The population in this study comprises students from the Tourism Department who participated in learning activities using the Wordwall application. A qualitative descriptive approach is employed to evaluate the outcomes of the practical sessions and analyze the gaps in vocabulary mastery based on the type of games, questions, and discussion topics. The findings from this analysis may also offer recommendations for improving teaching strategies aimed at enhancing vocabulary mastery, which, in turn, impacts English conversational skills.

METHOD

This research employed a descriptive qualitative approach with a focus on evaluating English vocabulary mastery among hospitality students using the Wordwall application. Abdussamad (2021:30-31) outlines that qualitative approaches have the following characteristics: 1) The key to the qualitative approach is the direct and in-depth understanding of phenomena; 2) Compared to other instruments, humans are the most appropriate tool for understanding realities in the field; 3) Describing the phenomena obtained by researchers or the "meaning of data" by presenting evidence depends on the ability and sharpness of the researcher's analysis; 4) Emphasizes process over results or products; 5) Data analysis is inductive in nature; 6) Meaning is the primary concern in qualitative research, with researchers not capturing meaning from their perspective as outsiders, but from the viewpoint of participants involved in the process and interaction. Therefore, this method allowed the researcher to explore and deeply analyze students' vocabulary mastery within the hospitality context, considering the relevance and effectiveness of various types of games and topics tested and used within the application.

Meanwhile, the Wordwall application was selected as the learning medium due to its interactive capabilities in presenting vocabulary-based games that can engagingly facilitate practice. Aprilia et al. (2023) indicated in their study that wordwall not only enhances students' language abilities through enjoyable evaluations but can also be optimized to meet the unique needs of students in rural areas. The study emphasized the importance of teachers' skills in using Wordwall to encourage creative thinking in designing evaluation questions. In this study, the games used on Wordwall included wordsearch, anagram, gameshow quiz, and match-up, designed to test students' vocabulary comprehension across various topics related to the hospitality sector.

Furthermore, this method was chosen based on the constructivism theory put forward by Saksono et al. (2023: 1-3) in their book, which asserts that the constructivist approach emphasizes the active role of individuals in constructing knowledge and understanding through the creation of meaning based on experience, thought, and reflection. This theory focuses on how individuals form knowledge and understand the world based on their context and personal experiences. Using Wordwall games provides students with the opportunity to create their own engaging and enjoyable learning experiences, solve problems through the games, gain direct experience, and reflect on their performance based on the immediate feedback received from the vocabulary testing process.

The population of this study comprised students from the Tourism Department at Universitas Negeri Gorontalo for the even semester of the 2023-2024 academic year. A sample of 26 students, who participated in various practical topics using the Wordwall application, was selected using purposive sampling techniques. Wijaya (2020) states that sample selection in qualitative research should be based on relevance to the research objectives and problems. In this context, the researcher's judgment becomes crucial to ensure that the information collected is adequate and appropriate, enabling the research results to effectively address the research questions posed.

The instrument used to collect data in this study was direct observation. Wijaya (2020) mentions that direct observation involves the researcher directly observing the research object without intermediaries, allowing the researcher to witness the conditions and phenomena occurring in the object. Therefore, this study was conducted by directly observing what happened to the research object, namely English vocabulary mastery in seven vocabulary test topics in the hospitality sector using the Wordwall application. The test design was created by selecting four types of games available through the application, such as a wordsearch for finding words, a gameshow quiz for choosing word options based on sentences, an anagram for rearranging letters into words, and a match-up for matching terms with their definitions. Data were collected from the practice activities carried out by the students using the Wordwall application.

Additionally, the research instrument was developed based on relevant topics in the hospitality sector, such as Basic Hotel Vocabulary, Travel and Tourism Terminology, Hotel Systems and Operations, Hotel Services and Amenities, Room Types, Marketing and Promotion, and Hotel Department Functions. This instrument was designed to comprehensively evaluate vocabulary comprehension by applying a context-based learning approach. Contextual learning is a teaching approach that allows instructors to connect the material taught in the classroom with real-world situations and encourages students to link the knowledge they have with its application in their personal life, family, and community (Muhartini, Mansur, A., & Bakar, A., 2023). Thus, in this learning process, the lecturer relates the evaluation topics to the context faced in the hospitality field. Each student completed a series of games designed to test vocabulary mastery in various

hospitality topics. The data collected included scores, completion time, and correct or incorrect answers in each game.

This data collection was based on authentic assessment, emphasizing that good evaluation must be based on tangible and accurate evidence of the competencies possessed by students, covering affective, cognitive, and psychomotor aspects, so that it can meet the core and basic competency demands of each subject (Sani, 2022). The data were analyzed qualitatively by categorizing the scores obtained, the completion time for each topic, and identifying patterns in correct and incorrect answers. Data analysis was conducted qualitatively by categorizing scores and completion times for each topic, as well as identifying patterns in correct and incorrect answers. This analysis was based on qualitative data analysis theory, which emphasizes the importance of understanding data in context and seeking deep meaning from evidence (Halijah, 2013). The validity of the research results was checked through data triangulation by comparing the test results from the practice activities using the wordwall application with direct observation. This procedure supports data validity theory, which suggests using various data sources to ensure the accuracy of findings (Sugiyono, 2012). This research method is expected to provide a deep understanding of student's vocabulary mastery levels and the effectiveness of the games in enhancing comprehension through the Wordwall application, as well as identify aspects that need improvement in developing learning strategies.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The main focus examined in this research includes 1) The level of English vocabulary mastery among students in the hospitality sector; 2) The most challenging topics for students; and 3) The effectiveness of using four game-based media in the Wordwall application for vocabulary mastery. Based on the data analysis results, several research questions have been answered as follows:

A. Level of English Vocabulary Mastery in the Hospitality Sector

The first focus of this research is the level of English vocabulary mastery in the Hospitality Sector. The vocabulary mastery examined in this study covers seven topics within the hospitality sector using four types of games available in the Wordwall application. The research results reveal several findings as follows:

In the first test on the topic "**Basic Hotel Vocabulary**," students were assessed using the "**wordsearch**" game, aimed at testing their mastery of basic hospitality vocabulary commonly encountered. The results showed that, on average, students could correctly answer 6.3 out of 10 words, with an average score of 62.68%. This indicates a good understanding, although there are still some aspects that need improvement on the tested topic. A perfect score (10) in this test was achieved by three students with initials (DDB, FOR, SWD). The completion time for this test varied among students, ranging from the fastest to the slowest, but this can be analyzed as not being the primary indicator of mastery. The fastest completion time for each question was 4.1 seconds, with a total time of 16.3 seconds, achieved by a student with the initials (AB). The test result for this student (AB) was only four correct answers. Two other students with the lowest scores, one scoring 1 (DPM) with a completion time of 17.8 seconds, and another scoring 2 (AK) with a completion time of 15.4 seconds.

The next test topic was "**Travel and Tourism Terminology**." Students were assessed using the "**Anagram**" game, which involved 25 words. This type of word game tests students' ability to correctly arrange scrambled words. All students managed to achieve a perfect score of 25 out of 25 words, indicating a very good vocabulary mastery related to the travel and tourism industry. Although there were varying score levels and different completion times, ranging from the fastest to the slowest. The fastest completion time was 1.3 seconds, with a total time of 5 minutes 57 seconds, achieved by a student with the initials (SWD). The top score was 323, with a total completion time of 10 minutes 56 seconds, achieved by a student with the initials (SB). On average, the score obtained was 288.88, and when compared to the highest score, is equal to 89%.

On the topic "**Hotel System and Operations**," students were faced with the "**Match Up**" game to match sentences with the correct vocabulary. Out of 26 students, only two managed to answer all the questions correctly. However, most students received scores ranging from 4 to 7 out of 10, indicating a basic understanding that needs improvement. Three students did not manage to answer any questions correctly, showing that this topic posed a significant challenge. The completion time for the questions varied among students. The fastest completion time for each question was 11 minutes 9 seconds, with a total completion time of 35 minutes 8 seconds, achieved by a student with the initials (ARM). However, in this test, the completion time for each question and the total completion time did not determine the number of correct answers. The best score was achieved by two students with the initials (HL, with a total completion time of

2 minutes 32 seconds, and FOR, with a total completion time of 10 minutes 36 seconds). On the other hand, two students with the initials NMAW (27.9 seconds) and DPM (1 minute 25 seconds) did not manage to answer any questions correctly. Overall, the level of mastery described in this test was low, with an average score of 37%.

Meanwhile, on the topic "**Hotel Services and Amenities**," using the "**Gameshow Quiz**" game, the majority of students were able to answer 7 to 8 out of 10 questions correctly, demonstrating a very good understanding. However, some students faced difficulties, with one student not answering any questions correctly and two others only answering 4 or 5 questions correctly, indicating the need for further clarification on some vocabulary. The average score on this topic was 1202.3, with the highest score of 1702 achieved by a student with the initials (PA). Out of the 10 questions provided, (PA) managed to get 9 correct answers and 1 incorrect answer. However, in this test, a student with the initials (HL) managed to get 10 correct answers but only achieved a total score below (PA) of 1530. In this test, the completion time was not mentioned, but the average score percentage obtained by students when compared to the top score was 71%.

The topic "**Room Types**" was evaluated using the "**Match Up**" game, where the average student score was 5.4 out of 10. Two students achieved a perfect score of 10 out of 10, demonstrating excellent vocabulary mastery, with one of them completing the test in the fastest time, 8.0 seconds, with a total time of 1 minute 04 seconds, achieved by a student with the initials (AFM). The fastest completion time for each question in this test did not indicate the number of correct answers, as even though (AFM) achieved the fastest time, this student only managed to get 8 correct answers and 2 incorrect answers. Meanwhile, two students with perfect scores were achieved by initials (FOR, with a completion time of 4 minutes 08 seconds, and SCA, with a completion time of 1 minute 49 seconds).

On the topic "**Marketing and Promotion**," evaluated using the "**Match Up**" game, students achieved an average score of 4.8 out of 10, indicating moderate understanding that requires improvement. One student with the initials (AFM) completed each question in 5.6 seconds. This shows high efficiency in understanding vocabulary, although this did not indicate the accuracy of the answers provided. (AFM) managed to get 8 correct and 2 incorrect answers, with a total completion time of 44.7 seconds. On the other hand, three students achieved a perfect score of 10 out of 10, with a total completion time of 1 minute 45 seconds by a student with the initials (PA), 1 minute 35 seconds by a student with the initials (SCA), and 2 minutes 13 seconds by a student with the initials (RPP). In this test, three students did not manage to answer any questions correctly, with initials (AVM – 39.7 seconds), (DPM – 34.9 seconds), and (AB – 20.6 seconds). Overall, the students' vocabulary mastery in this test showed moderate success, with an average score of 48%.

The seventh topic analyzed was "**Hotel Department Functions**." In this test, students were given the "**Match Up**" game, where they achieved an average score of 5.9 out of 10, indicating good mastery related to this topic. Six students achieved a perfect score of 10 out of 10 questions. The fastest completion time for each question was 5.8 seconds, achieved by a student with the initials (DDB) with a total completion time of 57.8 seconds. The other five who achieved perfect scores were students with the initials (KY, with a total completion time of 1 minute 35 seconds), (HL, with a total completion time of 1 minute 53 seconds), (FOR, with a total completion time of 2 minutes 44 seconds), (PA, with a total completion time of 2 minutes 14 seconds), and (SCA, with a total completion time of 1 minute 13 seconds). The results show variation in vocabulary mastery, with general terms in hotel operations being more easily understood by students, as indicated by the higher success rates. In this test, students received an average score of 59%.

Overall, the results of this study indicate that while there is a good understanding of hospitality vocabulary in some topics, there are also areas that require more attention and improvement in learning. Below is a summary of the student's vocabulary mastery level:

Table 1. Percentage of Student Scores

Topic	Average Score Percentage	Best Score	Top Score Achievers	Activity
Travel and Tourism Terminology	89%	323	1 student	Anagram
Hotel Services and Amenities	71%	1702	1 student	Gameshow Quiz
Basic Hotel Vocabulary	63%	10	3 students	Wordsearch

Hotel Department Functions	59 %	10	6 students	Match Up
Room Types	54%	10	2 students	Match Up
Marketing and Promotion	48%	10	3 students	Match Up
Hotel Systems and Operations	37 %	10	2 students	Match Up

B. Identification of Challenging Questions and Topics

This study provides clear insights into the vocabulary mastery of students across various topics related to the hospitality sector. Generally, students demonstrate varying levels of vocabulary understanding, with some topics being more readily comprehended than others.

In the Basic Hotel Vocabulary topic, words such as "Amenities" and "Guests" emerged as major challenges, with many students struggling to answer these terms correctly. This indicates the need for focused instruction on less familiar terms like additional facilities and common terms for guests.

In the Travel and Tourism Terminology topic, all students completed the anagram exercise, although some required more time. This suggests that the vocabulary is reasonably familiar, though quicker recognition would benefit from additional practice.

For the Hotel Systems and Operations topic, sentences related to the time between booking and guest arrival and the global computer network for transactions were the most challenging, with many students providing incorrect answers. This underscores the need for a more in-depth focus on these concepts.

In the Hotel Services and Amenities topic, some students found it difficult to answer more technical or less familiar questions. This indicates that this topic could benefit from further elaboration to ensure better comprehension.

In the Room Types topic, students were generally more adept at answering questions about common room types, while more technical terms such as "suite located on the top floor" or "room with a separate area" posed challenges. This suggests that less common concepts require additional explanation and practice.

The Marketing and Promotion topic also presented challenges, particularly regarding sales techniques like upselling and cross-selling and customer management concepts, which were less familiar to students. More interactive or case-based teaching methods are needed to improve understanding.

Finally, in the Hotel Department Functions topic, performance management and investment evaluation concepts were the most difficult, with many students providing incorrect answers. A more comprehensive teaching approach is required to address these difficulties and enhance mastery of more technical vocabulary.

In conclusion, this study identifies the topics and questions that pose challenges for students, providing a clear reference for focusing future instructional efforts.

Table 2. Difficulty Level of Questions and Game Types

Topic	Game Types	Difficulty Level	Difficulty Analysis
Hotel System and Operations	Match- Up	High	High difficulty, particularly with concepts of stay duration and booking time.
Hotel Department Function	Match- Up	Medium to High	Difficulty in understanding complex operational procedures.
Room Types	Match- Up	Medium	Difficulty in distinguishing between similar room types.
Marketing and Promotion	Match- Up	Medium	Difficulty with effective marketing and promotion strategies.
Travel and Tourism Terminology	Anagram	High	High difficulty, requiring letter arrangement and quick thinking. On average, students need around 13 minutes to finish the task.
Services and Amenities	Gameshow Quiz	Low to Medium	Relatively low difficulty, but some terms are still challenging.
Basic Hotel Sector	Wordsearch	Low to Medium	Relatively low difficulty, most students performed well.

C. Effectiveness of Game Types on Vocabulary Comprehension

The study evaluated the effectiveness of various game types on students' understanding of hotel sector vocabulary.

1. **Basic Hotel Sector:** The "Wordsearch" game proved effective for recognizing and locating vocabulary within the text. Terms like "Administration" and "Operations" were easily identified by most students, while "Amenities" and "Guest" posed more difficulty, highlighting areas where additional focus is needed.
2. **Travel and Tourism Terminology:** The "Anagram" game effectively tested students' ability to rearrange tourism-related words. Although all students achieved maximum scores, the significant variation in completion times revealed differences in processing speed and word arrangement skills.
3. **Hotel System and Operations:** The "Match-Up" game successfully assessed comprehension in contextual sentences. It showed a broad range of understanding among students, suggesting its utility in evaluating vocabulary skills within specific contexts.
4. **Hotel Services and Amenities:** The "Gameshow Quiz" format engaged students and generally improved their vocabulary understanding. However, performance varied with completion time, indicating that while the game was motivating, it also impacted results based on individual speed.
5. **Room Types:** The "Match-Up" game demonstrated the potential for enhancing vocabulary comprehension by matching terms with definitions. Difficulty with specific or less common terms suggests a need for more detailed instructional support.
6. **Marketing and Promotion:** The "Match-Up" game effectively reinforced vocabulary related to marketing and promotion. However, the relatively low average scores indicated that some students might benefit from additional or alternative learning methods to fully grasp complex concepts.
7. **Hotel Department Functions:** The "Match-Up" game effectively measured understanding of operational vocabulary. It highlighted the need for more detailed teaching on specific management and performance topics, as students required additional examples and explanations to master these concepts.

CONCLUSION

Based on the analysis of data from seven evaluated game activities, it can be concluded that the vocabulary proficiency of Tourism students at Universitas Negeri Gorontalo for the 2023-2024 academic year varies within the hospitality sector. The categories "Travel and Tourism Terminology" exhibit very good results with average scores at 89%. In the "Hotel Services and Amenities" category, the average scores was 71%. Meanwhile, for the "Basic Hotel Vocabulary", students averaged at 63%, followed by "Hotel Department Functions" at 59% and "Room Types" at 54%, and "Marketing and Promotion" at 48%. Students score the lowest in the "Hotel Systems and Operations" category at 37%. The greatest difficulties are identified with technical and specific vocabulary related to topics such as hotel systems and marketing techniques, indicating a need for improvements in teaching and learning materials.

Furthermore, based on the difficulty levels of the questions and the games used, it can be concluded that the "wordsearch" and "gameshow quiz" games have low to medium difficulty levels, while the "match-up" game has medium to high difficulty level. The "anagram" game presents high difficulty due to the requirement for quick and logical thinking. The gaps observed in topics such as "Hotel System and Operations" and "Hotel Department Functions" highlight the need for additional emphasis on these areas in the curriculum. Although the "wordsearch" and "gameshow quiz" games are relatively easier, some terms still require deeper understanding. This study emphasizes the importance of integrating interactive teaching methods in vocabulary learning, as well as the need for further adjustment and development of learning materials to address the identified gaps in understanding.

In conclusion, based on the analysis of the effectiveness of game types on student understanding, each method has its strengths and challenges. The Wordsearch game is effective for recognizing and finding basic hotel vocabulary, though some terms remain difficult to locate, necessitating a focus on more challenging terms. The anagram game effectively tests students' ability to rearrange tourism-related words, but variations in completion times suggest a need for speed practice. The match-up game, used for hotel systems and operations, hotel services and amenities, room types, and hotel department functions, is effective for associating terms with definitions, although differences in results and completion times indicate a need for additional materials and a more detailed approach to teaching. The gameshow quiz motivates active participation and enhances engagement in vocabulary learning, but variations in completion times affect the

final results, indicating the need for strategies to accelerate completion times and boost motivation. Overall, a combination of game methods can enhance vocabulary understanding by tailoring the approach to the specific challenges faced by students.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Recommendations for Lecturers:

- It is recommended to develop instructional materials with a particular focus on high-difficulty topics such as "Hotel System and Operation" and "Marketing and Promotion." This approach should include more comprehensive methods, such as case studies and practical simulations, to deepen students' understanding of technical and specific vocabulary.
- Additionally, enhancing and diversifying teaching methods and types of games to accommodate varying student abilities is advisable. Introducing games that emphasize contextual understanding and real-world application of vocabulary is expected to improve instructional effectiveness.
- Increasing the frequency of practical exercises and providing continuous, constructive feedback is crucial. Consistent evaluation and additional practice should be implemented to address deficiencies in vocabulary comprehension and application.

2. Recommendations for Students:

Students are encouraged to actively engage in practical exercises and utilize feedback to improve their vocabulary understanding. Regular practice and the integration of learned vocabulary into real-world situations will facilitate better mastery of the vocabulary.

3. Recommendations for Institutions or Departments:

- It is advised to enhance the Wordwall platform to better meet vocabulary learning needs. Developing additional game formats that stimulate deeper vocabulary comprehension should be considered to improve learning effectiveness.
- Further research is recommended to explore the impact of variables such as educational background and work experience on vocabulary mastery. Additionally, evaluating alternative learning technologies in this context could provide further insights into the effectiveness of different instructional methods.

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